

PREFORM INFLUENCE ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF STIFFENED PANELS MANUFACTURED BY LIQUID RESIN INFUSION

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This paper deals with the influence of preform type on the impact resistance of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) stiffened panels. This work is part of the CoSPI project that aims at studying out-of-autoclave processes for manufacturing aeronautical primary structure parts. Out-of-autoclave processes are studied for their lower costs and environmental impact when compared to prepreg processes widely used for primary structure parts [1]. In this paper, stiffened panels produced using the LRI process are considered. With this process, dry fabrics are laid up, thus complex geometries such as blade stiffeners have to be preformed before infusing. The influence of the type of preform used on the mechanical properties of the part is studied. Two types of preforms are used: powdered and knitted preforms.

1 Trade-off study

The first step of CoSPI project involves studying several out-of-autoclave manufacturing processes. Three main processes have been tested: Resin Film Infusion, Liquid Resin Infusion and cold infusion. Two or three different resins have been tested for each process. The experimental set-up used is detailed in Fig. 1 below. For all the tested panels, the same type of carbon fabric has been used.

1.1 Carbon fabrics

In order to perform all the mechanical tests, two panels were produced for each set of parameters: a unidirectional (UD) panel and a quasi-isotropic panel. Thus, 32 panels were produced for the trade-off study. All the panels were produced with unidirectional carbon fabrics made from High Resistance fibers (6K HR yarn). The nominal weight of the UD carbon fabric is 205 g/m².

1.2 Processes

In the past ten years, more and more products dedicated to infusion processes have been launched on the market in order to simplify the preparation of an infusion. Thus, many processes based on infusion have emerged. For this study, two of them have been selected, Resin Film Infusion (RFI) and Liquid Infusion (heated or not). Liquid infusion is the usual process and we chose to separate cold infusion and Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI). The only difference comes from the necessity to heat the resin or not during infusion. For cold infusion, infusion is performed at room temperature whereas for LRI, the resin and the toolings are heated and infusion is performed at temperatures around 100°C. For each of these processes two or three resins have been tested; they are presented in the next paragraph.

1.3 Resins

The chosen resins needed to validate several criteria: a glass transition temperature above 120°C and good impact resistance, compatible with primary structure expectations. The tested resins are presented in Tab. 1 below.

The M21 resin used the in-autoclave RFI process is defined as our reference. Indeed, this resin-process combination is very close to the prepreg process. The resin M21 is exactly the same and the curing in an autoclave respects the same cycle as that of M21 prepreps. Thus, this reference will be used to compare the mechanical test results obtained with the other resin-process couples.

1.4 Mechanical tests

All the process-resin couples have been tested with several mechanical tests: traction on UD 0° and 90° and on quasi-isotropic coupons (ASTM D3039), Filled Hole Tension tests are also performed.

Compression tests (ASTM D695 on UD 0°, UD 90° and on quasi-isotropic coupons and Open Hole Compression) and Compression After Impact tests. Shear tests are also performed by means of tensile tests on $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]_{3s}$ coupons. All these standard tests are detailed in [2].

The results of the trade-off study presented Fig. 1 are summed up in the next paragraph.

2 Mechanical tests results

2.1 Tensile tests

All the tensile tests on UD 0°, UD 90° and quasi-isotropic lay-ups have been performed according to ASTM D3039 standard.

The results on UD 90° are interesting for resin comparison. The ultimate stresses obtained with the selected resins are presented in Fig. 2 below.

Two resin-process couples present significantly higher performances: autoclave RFI M21 and LRI Cytec (in autoclave or in oven). The relative deviation between the ultimate stress obtained with the reference and the autoclave LRI Cytec is only -3% and -7% with the LRI Cytec out of autoclave.

Tensile tests on coupons with an isotropic lay-up show a slight improvement in the ultimate stress for autoclave processes (Fig. 3). Nevertheless, no resin-process couple shows a significant improvement in the ultimate stress.

A final tensile test was performed: Filled Hole Tension. Quasi-isotropic coupons were drilled and the 6mm hole was filled with a fastener. The fastener used was a 6mm bolt with two washers. The fastener torque applied was 10 N.m with a torque wrench. A tensile test was then performed on the coupons according to ASTM D6742 standard. The results are presented in Fig. 4.

The out-of-autoclave LRI Cytec obtained the best results, along with autoclave M36 and autoclave epolam (relative deviation of +15% with the autoclave M21 reference).

2.2 Compression tests

Compression tests, as with the tensile tests, have been performed on UD 0°, UD 90° and quasi-isotropic lay-up. The compression tests comply with ASTM D695 standard. This test is suitable for comparative purposes but the ultimate stresses and modulus values identified should be considered with care as stated in [3].

The results presented in Fig. 5 show that out-of-autoclave LRI Cytec is also very efficient in compression with performances close to the M21 autoclave. Resoltech resins HTG180E and HTG160 are also efficient when they are cured in an autoclave.

Another compression test has been performed on drilled coupons: Open Hole Compression test (ASTM D6484). For this test, liquid infusion autoclave processes give poorer results than the same processes carried out in oven. The reference M21 autoclave resin gives the better results just ahead of Cytec resin out-of-autoclave (relative deviation of -3%). All the results are shown in Fig. 6.

2.3 Compression After Impact

These tests were very important for the project, as the compression residual stress is an important characteristic for primary structures. They were performed on a drop tower at IFREMER, Brest. The impact energy was calibrated in order to produce a Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID). Thus, the impacts were performed with an energy of 15J in accordance with ASTM D7136. The impact was also barely visible on the non impacted faces of the coupons produced with the resins formulated with thermoplastics (LY3598, HTG180E).

Nevertheless, residual compression stress was low for the coupons made with these resins when compared to autoclave M21 or LRI Cytec coupons. See Fig. 7

2.4 Shear tests

In-plane shear tests have been carried out from tensile tests on $[+45/-45]_{3s}$ coupons. These tests are detailed in ASTM D3518 [2]. Longitudinal and transversal strain measurements are required for this test. They were performed using digital image correlation (Aramis by GOM system).

In this test, autoclave RFI panels perform best (M21 and M36). Some other resin-process couples are near these best results: out-of-autoclave LRI cytec (relative deviation of -4.5% on the modulus and -6.5% on the ultimate stress), autoclave Resoltech resins (-12% deviation) and out-of-autoclave HTG160 (-13% deviation). All these results are detailed in Fig. 8.

2.5 Conclusion on the trade-off study

All these mechanical tests, representing 880 coupons, have shown that the out-of-autoclave process can fulfill required criteria for primary structure parts. One resin-process couple is particularly interesting with regard to its mechanical properties: out-of-autoclave LRI Cytec. Manufacturing costs are also lower and confirm the current strong interest for this process even for primary structure parts as stated in [3]. Thus, LRI Cytec has been chosen for stiffened panels production. In order to produce a stiffener, preforms have to be made before the infusion. Two types of preforms have been studied in the project: powdered and knitted preforms.

3 Stiffened panels production

3.1 Process retained

The first step of CoSPI project has shown that panels produced by LRI present mechanical properties and damage resistance close to those of panels made with prepreg and cured in an autoclave. Thus, this process has been chosen for this study in order to compare the influence of the type of preform on the mechanical behavior and the impact resistance of infused stiffened panels.

The infusion set-up is detailed in Fig. 9. The carbon fabrics used are the same as those used for the trade-off study. The lay-up sequence for the skin is the following [+45/-45/+45/-45/0/90]_s. The lay-up sequence for the blade stiffener is [+45/-45/0/90/+45/-45]_s: see Fig. 10. The resin employed is Prism EP2400 from Cytec.

The infusion is performed from above: the resin migrates into the skin lay-up through the thickness. It finally climbs into the stiffener to finish the part. The vacuum is pulled using a “through the vacuum bag” connector. This connector can be placed anywhere on the skin as a breather is placed between the vacuum bag and the microporous membrane in order to drain the vacuum all over the infusion lay-up.

A permeable counter mold has been used in order to obtain two clean shape surfaces on the panel. This counter mold is a 1mm drilled aluminum sheet.

Two metallic angles have been placed against the preform in order to compact the blade stiffener. They have been covered with an adhesive PTFE glass fabric for demolding. These angles can slide on

the counter mold in order to guarantee the compaction of the preform and avoid any wrinkles.

3.2 Preform production

The infusion process requires the use of dry fabrics to produce the part. These dry preforms are difficult to handle. In order to infuse complex shapes, several preforming techniques may be used. The use of adhesive sprays is common in the shipbuilding industry. For higher productivity rates, epoxy powder can be applied to the fabric (on one or two sides) after weaving. Preforms can also be obtained by knitting the fabrics into the desired shape. The choice between these techniques depends on the part size, its shape complexity and the number of parts to manufacture. For this project, powdered and knitted preforms have been considered. The preforms are used for the blade stiffener before their assembly with the panel skin.

3.2.1 Powdered preforms

The powdered preforms were obtained by heating between 80°C and 100°C the one-side powdered carbon fabrics formed on a specific tool. The fabrics were vacuum-compressed to the tools.

After heating in an oven for 30mins at 100°C, the preform is obtained and can be easily handled for preparing the infusion of the stiffened panel.

3.2.2 Knitted preforms

Another way to obtain a preform that can be handled for preparing an infusion is to knit the dry carbon fabrics. For the considered blade stiffeners, preforms were knitted using a 200 denier aramid (Kevlar) yarn. The density of the stitches is 1.54 per cm².

The influence of the stitches on the impact resistance has often been studied in the literature [5]. The influence of a powdered preform on the mechanical behavior of the finished part, however, has rarely been investigated [6] and never for cold or Liquid Resin infusion. Several mechanical tests were performed on flat and stiffened panels in order to emphasize the preform influence. These tests are presented in the next section.

4 Mechanical tests on powdered panels

4.1 Standard tests overview

First of all, standard tests were carried out on flat panels. Four panels were made. Two of them were composed of UD carbon fabrics without any

powdering. The remaining two were manufactured using one-side powdered carbon fabrics.

The tests were as follows: traction on UD 0°, UD 90° and quasi-isotropic lay-up (ASTM D3039), Compression on the same lay-up sequences (ASTM D695), In-plane shear response by tensile test of a $\pm 45^\circ$ Laminate (ASTM D3518), Filled Hole Tension and Open Hole Compression (ASTM D6742 and D6484).

The influence of the preform can then be analyzed by comparing test results between powdered and non powdered preforms.

4.2 Results comparison

The relative deviation between the mechanical results on powdered and non powdered coupons is reported in Fig. 11. Most tests have revealed a very slight influence of the epoxy powder on the mechanical results. The relative deviation is below 7% for all the tests except for traction on UD 90° and Filled Hole Tension.

The differences observed on this last test could be due to the preparation of the powdered coupons. The finish on the coupon edges obtained after waterjet cutting was not sharp and may have induced lower performances.

Concerning traction on UD 90°, the mean result for ultimate stress obtained for powdered coupons is 16% lower than the mean results on non powdered coupons. The ultimate stress is 65.5MPa for non powdered coupons and 55MPa for powdered ones. The standard deviation for these two series of five coupons is 9MPa. This standard deviation is quite high and could be due to small porosities in the resin that initiate the failure of the coupons. On UD 90°, the resin is stressed and leads to failure, so this lay-up is highly dependent on small defects present in the resin. This observation is confirmed by autoclave processes, which tend to minimize the size of defects as the pressure increases [7]. Indeed, the standard deviation for ultimate tensile stress on UD 90° with autoclave LRI Cytac is only 2MPa.

The other mechanical property that is studied is the impact resistance using a Compression After Impact test and non destructive tests on impacted stiffened panels. The tests and the results are presented in the following paragraph.

4.3 Impact tests

4.3.1 Compression After Impact tests

Drop impact tests have been performed on flat panels to perform Compression After Impact tests (ASTM D7137).

An energy of 15J was chosen as reported previously in 2.3. Then, Compression After Impact tests were performed on the impacted panels. Powdered and non powdered coupons again showed similar results for compression residual strength: see Fig. 11.

4.3.2 Impacted stiffened panels

The stiffened panels have a different geometry than the flat coupons used for Compression After Impact. The panel dimensions are 200mm x 200mm with a blade stiffener shown in Fig. 10.

Thus, the energy impact had to be modified in order to obtain barely visible impact damage. An energy of 30J was finally chosen. We noticed that stiffener delamination occurs at this energy level whereas the impacted face remains intact.

First of all, the impacted panels were compared by measuring the delaminated areas using non destructive ultrasonic C-scans (see Fig.12). For both types of preforms, one side of the stiffener is fully debonded. The other side is partially debonded. For both panels, the results are very similar. The non debonded zones (with a thickness of 4mm in Fig. 12) present the same surface and position.

The displacements were also measured using 3D scan before and after impact. A comparison of the two scans for a section in the middle of the coupons clearly shows the debonding of the stiffener. A curved shape is also highlighted by this measurement due to the debonding of the stiffener with the skin of the panel.

5 Conclusion

The use of different preform processes has been investigated in this study. After a trade-off study concerning the out-of-autoclave process, the LRI process with Cytac Prism EP2400 resin was selected for its high mechanical performances (in static and also in impact resistance). The comparison with the autoclave RFI process showed that this out-of-autoclave process could fulfill all requirements for primary structures.

Stiffened panels were then produced. The panels present an indexed blade stiffener on a flat skin. Powdered and knitted preforms were studied for the stiffener manufacturing. First of all, mechanical tests

showed that epoxy powder has only a slight influence on the mechanical properties of the composite. The maximum tensile stress for UD 90° was the only parameter significantly impacted by the powdering. Surprisingly, neither the in-plane shear resistance nor the impact resistance are reduced.

Finally, impact test were performed on panels presenting a stiffener manufactured with a powder preform or with a knitted preform. Once again, the impact behavior was not influenced by the powder. These results are very encouraging for the development of automatic dry fiber deposition using epoxy powder for holding plies together.

An extension of this study could be carried out by verifying whether the powder also has no impact on out of plane shear behavior. Furthermore, the quantity of powder used remained the same in this study. It could be interesting to verify whether a larger quantity could lead to variations in the mechanical properties of the composite.

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Fig. 1. Experimental set-up used

Fig. 2. UD 90° ultimate stress

Fig. 3. Quasi-isotropic coupons: ultimate stress

Fig. 4. Filled Hole Tension: ultimate stress

Fig. 5. Compression tests results on UD 0°, UD 90° and quasi-iso coupons

Fig. 6. Open Hole Compression: ultimate stress

Fig. 7. Compression After Impact: ultimate stress

Fig. 8. Ultimate shear stress

Fig. 9. LRI set-up for blade stiffened panels

Fig. 10. Blade stiffener geometry and lay-up

Fig. 11. Relative deviation between results of standard tests on powdered and non powdered coupons

Fig. 12. C-scans on impacted stiffened panels with knitted preform (left) and powdered preform (right)

Fig. 13. Displacements in mm between impacted and non impacted panels with powdered and knitted preforms

Process	Reference	Choice motivation
RFI	Hexcel M21	Certified resin and reference for our trade off study.
	Hexcel M36	Another certified resin (for prepregs)
LRI	Cytec Prism EP2400	Newly developed monocomponent resin for primary structure production
	Resoltech HTG180E	Resin with thermoplastic addition for improving the impact behavior
	Huntsman LY3598	In development resin for aeronautic industry
Cold Infusion	Epolam 2035	Resin with $T_g > 120^\circ\text{C}$
	Huntsman LY5052	Resin with $T_g > 120^\circ\text{C}$
	Resoltech HTG160	Resin for structural parts with $T_g = 160^\circ\text{C}$

Tab 1. Resins used for the trade-off study